

Секція 4. ХІМІЧНІ, ФІЗИЧНІ, МАТЕМАТИЧНІ МЕТОДИ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ЯКОСТІ ПРОДУКТІВ ХАРЧУВАННЯ

UDC 631.563.8:635.646

SUBSTANTIATION OF THE FILM-FORMING COMPOSITION FOR EGGPLANT FRUITS TREATMENT BEFORE STORAGE

A. Dubinina, T. Letuta, T. Frolova, O. Skyrda, I. Belyaeva, T. Popova

The micro- and mycobiota of the fresh eggplant fruits phyllosphere of different botanical varieties Valentyna and Samurai (Japanese agriculture), Clorinda (Egg agriculture), Solaris (American agriculture) was studied. The possibility of oak bark and leaves, juniper berries, St. John's wort, costmary, common plantain, wormwood and motherwort extracts use is considered. It is recommended to use extracts of oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and St. John's wort on the base of studies of medicinal and vegetable raw material extracts potential toxicity. The studied extracts have antimicrobial activity against 4 reference strains: E. coli ATCC 25922, S. aureus ATCC 25923, P. aeruginosa ATCC 27853, C. albicans ATCC 885-653. Fungal growth inhibition zones are identified in the studied samples compositions: Cladosporium from 15 mm to 28 mm, Fusarium from 18 mm to 30 mm, Rhizopus from 16 mm to 30 mm. The effect of the film-forming agent type on the fungal culture growth inhibition is studied. It is determined that the medicinal and vegetable raw material extracts composition with chitosan use as film-forming agent has the greatest fungistatic properties. The studies results show the dependence of respiratory intensity on the eggplant fruits variety. The use of film-forming composition of medicinal and vegetable extracts on the base of low molecular weight chitosan reduces the amplitude of eggplant fruits respiration and allows storage prolonging by 2,0–2,3 times.

Keywords: eggplant, epiphytic microflora, toxicity, antimicrobial activity, film-forming agent, respiration rate, chitosan.

ОБҐРУНТУВАННЯ СКЛАДУ ПЛІВКОУТВОРЮВАЛЬНОЇ КОМПОЗИЦІЇ ДЛЯ ОБРОБКИ ПЛОДІВ БАКЛАЖАНА ПЕРЕД ЗБЕРІГАННЯМ

**А.А. Дубініна, Т.М. Летуґа, Т.В. Фролова, О.Є. Скірда,
І.М. Беляєва, Т.М. Попова**

Досліджено мікро- та мікобіоти філосфери свіжих плодів баклажана різних ботанічних сортів. Визначено потенційну токсичність екстрактів лікарсько-технічної сировини. Обґрунтовано доцільність використання

© Дубініна А.А., Летуґа Т.М., Фролова Т.В., Скірда О.Є., Беляєва І.М.,
Попова Т.М., 2020

екстрактів кори та листя дуба, ягід ялівцю і трави звіробою звичайного. Подано оцінку антимікробної активності екстрактів. Визначено фунгіцидні властивості композицій екстрактів із різними співвідношеннями компонентів. Досліджено вплив типу плівкоутворювача на затримку росту культур цвілевих грибків. Досліджено вплив плівкоутворювальних композицій на інтенсивність дихання плодів баклажана.

Ключові слова: баклажан, епіфітна мікрофлора, токсичність, антимікробна активність, плівкоутворювач, інтенсивність дихання, хітозан.

ОБОСНОВАНИЕ СОСТАВА ПЛЕНКООБРАЗУЮЩЕЙ КОМПОЗИЦИИ ДЛЯ ОБРАБОТКИ ПЛОДОВ БАКЛАЖАНА ПЕРЕД ХРАНЕНИЕМ

**А.А. Дубинина, Т.Н. Летута, Т.В. Фролова, Е.Е. Скирда,
И.М. Беляева, Т.Н. Попова**

Исследована микро- и микобиота филосферы свежих плодов баклажана разных ботанических сортов. Определена потенциальная токсичность экстрактов лекарственно-технического сырья. Обоснована целесообразность использования экстрактов коры и листьев дуба, ягод можжевельника и травы зверобоя обыкновенного. Дана оценка антимикробной активности экстрактов. Определены фунгицидные свойства композиций экстрактов с разными соотношениями компонентов. Исследовано влияние типа пленкообразователя на задержку роста культур плесневых грибков. Исследовано влияние пленкообразующих композиций на интенсивность дыхания плодов баклажана.

Ключевые слова: баклажан, эпифитная микрофлора, токсичность, антимикробная активность, пленкообразователь, интенсивность дыхания, хитозан.

Statement of the problem. Vegetables are essential components of a healthy diet. Their value is conditioned by the vitamins, minerals and nutrients complex presence which have the ability of free radicals neutralizing. For Ukraine as country which focuses on the agricultural products export, vegetable products high quality is necessary condition for gaining access to the European market. According to FAO, 44% of all food resources losses are losses of fruits and vegetable raw material. The main reason of vegetables significant losses is their affection by microorganisms. The composition of the surface microflora is very diverse and random; it depends on the type of plant, geographical, climatic and other conditions.

Modern agricultural practice usually uses synthetic agents for food products processing, mostly contact fungicides with broad spectrum of action, which have unsatisfactory toxicological profile for the human body,

and in case of insufficient hygienic treatment by consumers can cause poisoning and health damage.

Therefore, the development of vegetables processing new agents on the base of harmless to human vegetable components is very important task of modern agricultural, phytochemical and biological industries.

Review of the latest research and publications. Currently, refrigerated storage is the main method of storing fresh fruits and vegetables. Despite the high cost, the efficiency of refrigerators use for fruits and vegetables storage is very high, because of natural weight loss and losses from microbiological and physiological diseases reduction. It also should be noted that the storage method in controlled gaseous medium has become widespread. The base of storage in the regulated gaseous medium is not the inhibition of phytopathogens of the microflora, but the regulation of metabolism, which prevents the occurrence of functional disorders and thus provides high resistance to infectious diseases. Another way of fruits' affecting during storage is treatment with chemicals. The following types of treatment are common: calcium preparations, synthetic antiseptics, ethylene-producing preparations, iodine-containing antiseptics, potassium metabisulfite.

The disadvantage of such technologies is the detrimental effects of these chemicals use on the human body. Innovative technologies of vegetable raw material storage by means of various physical factors of influence are currently developed. They include, for example, the technology of agricultural raw material long-term storage with use of raw material pre-treatment before storage by electromagnetic field [1–7]. Washing of vegetable raw material with tap, chlorinated, electroactivated and ozonated water has positive effect on microbiological purity and raw material quality during storage [8]. Different methods are used in addition to the use of various physical factors which affect on vegetable raw material for storage period increasing; these methods include not only the effect on the raw material, and also use of other various methods such as the bactericidal packaging, as well as various types of raw material pre-treatment before packaging [9–12]. Also natural extracts from various spicy-aromatic plants which have bactericidal effect are widely used in the food industry [13–15]. In addition currently storage methods on the base of various oxygen absorbents from packaging are used [16].

The objective of the research is the film-forming agent composition substantiation for eggplant fruits treatment before storage.

Purpose achieving includes the following tasks:

– study of fresh eggplant fruits composition epiphytic microflora;

- study of medicinal and technical raw material extracts potential toxicity;
- establishing of medicinal and technical raw material extracts antimicrobial activity;
- determination of medicinal and technical raw material extracts fungicidal properties;
- study of the film-forming agent type effect on the microorganisms growth;
- study of the fresh eggplant fruits, which are treated with film-forming composition respiration intensity.

Presentation of the research material. The research objects are: fresh eggplant fruits of Valentyna and Samurai varieties (Japanese agriculture), Clorinda (Egg agriculture), Solaris (American agriculture); extracts: oak bark and leaves, juniper berries, St. John's wort, costmary, common plantain, wormwood and motherwort; film-forming agents: chitosan, methylcellulose, sodium alginate; unprocessed eggplant fruits (K_1), eggplant fruits treated with «Tween» preparation (K_2), eggplant fruits treated with film-forming composition on the based of chitosan and medicinal and vegetable raw material extracts (Chitosan).

The total bacteria number, composition of the micro- and mycobiota of fresh eggplant fruits epiphytic microflora are determined with use of standard methods which are recommended for food products sanitary and bacteriological control [17; 18].

Studies of medicinal and technical raw material extracts potential toxicity were carried out by the bacteriological method, namely, by 5% blood agar inoculation [19]. Antimicrobial activity tests were carried out by sanitary bacteriology methods [20]. The extracts' fungicidal properties were studied according to the experimental mycology methods [21].

Fresh vegetables losses main cause is microbial damage. For a long time, fresh vegetables remain viable; there are various physiological processes in fresh vegetables. However, in contrast to vegetative plants, dissimilation processes (respiration) predominate in the gathered vegetables, and they also retain transpiration functions (water evaporation). Deep and irreversible changes in vegetables occur under intense biochemical processes. The storage period decreases and appearance deteriorates under vegetables aging. They gradually loosen, lose flavor and nutritional value; ability to diseases resisting reduces; various microorganisms begin to develop on their surface.

The plants resistance to microbial lesions is explained by many factors. Their anatomical structure, especially the integuments structure has significant importance. Peels (their thickness, suberization cells presence,

cuticles and wax bloom) are powerful protective barrier to the microbes' penetration into the vegetables pulp. The chemical composition, substances which inhibit microorganisms' development, such as dyes (anthocyanins, flavonols), essential oils and especially phytoncides also play important role. Many of these substances are concentrated mainly in the vegetables peel and adjacent pulp cells.

Various microorganisms are constantly on the surface of vegetables, great part of which is not involved in the disease and spoilage processes, and it is in inactive state. If the peel isn't damaged, then there is usually small amount of nutrients in it, so only some species of microorganisms which make up the so-called epiphytic microflora can exist and multiply on its surface. Vegetables infection with microorganisms can be active – the pathogen penetrates into the tissues through intact integuments and passive – the pathogen penetrates through damaged areas. Significant part of these microorganisms is in inactive state and after a while dies because of insufficient conditions for their development.

We carried out the general contamination study of eggplant fruits different botanical varieties. The research results are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Study of myco- and microbiota of eggplant fruits phyllosphere

Indicator (CFU in 1 cm ³)	Botanical varieties			
	Valentyana	Samurai	Clorinda	Solaris
QMAFAM	8,0x10 ⁴	1,2x10 ⁵	1,8x10 ⁵	4,3x10 ⁵
Bacterium of intestinal bacillus	–	–	–	–
Pathogenic enterobacteria	–	–	–	–
Enterococcus spp	–	–	–	–
Yeast fungi	–	–	–	–
Mold fungi	6,0x10 ⁴	4,1x10 ⁴	1,2x10 ⁵	6,7x10 ⁴
NFGNB	2,2x10 ²	4,4x10 ²	6,1x10 ²	4,1x10 ²

The total quantity of mesophilic aerobic and facultative anaerobic microorganisms (QMAFAM) is in the range from 8,0x10⁴ (Valentyana variety) to 4,3x10⁵ (Solaris variety). Bacteria of the Escherichia coli group, including coliform microorganisms, as well as pathogenic enterobacteria, including salmonella were not identified. However, during seeding on Endo medium, pink colonies with diameter of 1,0–1,5 mm in the amount of 2,2x10² to 6,1x10² CFU/g were identified. Under identifying these isolates on differential diagnostic media, they were classified as non-fermenting

gram-negative microorganisms. These microorganisms belong to the bacteria group which is the component of QMAFAM index. Bacteria of *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Xanthomonas* genus were also identified on fruits surface. The study of the eggplant fruits phyllosphere mycobiota composition shows the fungi presence of *Botrytis*, *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus* and *Cladosporium* genus. The genus *Fusarium* was predominant; all other fungi were represented by single colonies.

On the base of obtained data, we can conclude that the eggplant fruits epiphytic microflora is diverse; its composition has random character. With taking it into account, we used the principles of selection plants with the highest antimicrobial and antifungal activity against virulent pathogens of agricultural crops at the stage of film-forming composition for eggplant fruits treatment theoretical development. We considered the possibility of oak bark and leaves, juniper berries, common St. John's wort, costmary, plantain, wormwood and motherwort extracts use during the composition substantiation for eggplant fruits treatment. The potential toxicity of the samples was studied by extracts inoculating with 5% blood agar for herbal extracts safety assessment. Toxic compounds hemolyze erythrocytes and enlighten the bloodstream at the test site (erythrocyte lysis). The research obtained data are presented in table 2.

Table 2

Study of the medicinal and technical raw material extracts potential toxicity

№	Tested samples	The hemolysis zone diameter, mm
1	Oak bark and leaves	Hemolysis isn't observed
2	Common plantain	2
3	Juniper berries	Hemolysis isn't observed
4	Common St. John's wort	Hemolysis isn't observed
5	Costmary	5
6	Common wormwood	7
7	Motherwort	7

The study identified the blood agar lysis absence in samples № 1, 3, 4. Samples № 5, 6, 7 hemolyze erythrocyte cells, and relatively weak lysis was identified in sample № 2. Oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and common St. John's wort extracts were selected on the base of obtained results for eggplant fruits treatment and further research.

We used reference microorganisms' strains for the screening phase of the study for extracts antimicrobial activity assessment of medicinal and vegetable raw material. The reference rather than clinical strains of microorganisms use is one of the main requirements for the experimental conditions unification, which can significantly increase the reliability and comparability of the microbiological studies results. In accordance with the requirements of regulatory documentation, we used ATCC strains (American Type Culture Collection) of the following species of microorganisms: *E. coli* ATCC 25922, *S. aureus* ATCC 25923, *C. albicans* ATCC 885-653, *B. cereus* ATCC 537, *B. subtilis* ATCC 6633. The effect of medicinal and vegetable raw material extracts on the isolate, which is extracted from eggplants lavage fluid and the mold fungi isolate were also studied. The results are presented in table 3.

Table 3

Antimicrobial activity of the medicinal and vegetable raw material extracts

Reference strains and isolates	Oak bark and leaves extract	Juniper berries extract	St. John's wort herb extract
<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 25922	–	–	–
<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 25923	–	–	–
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> ATCC 27853	–	–	–
<i>C. albicans</i> ATCC 885-653	-	–	–
<i>B. cereus</i> ATCC 537	+	+	+
<i>B. subtilis</i> ATCC 6633	+	+	–
NFGNB "B" isolate	–	–	–
Mold fungi isolate	–	–	–
– growth absence, + microorganisms' growth.			

With taking into account the obtained data, we can conclude that the studied extracts have antimicrobial activity against 4 reference strains, namely: *E. coli* ATCC 25922, *S. aureus* ATCC 25923, *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *C. albicans* ATCC 885-653, to the isolate which is sown from the eggplant fruits lavage fluid and from mold fungi isolate. The reference strains *B. cereus* ATCC 537 and *B. subtilis* ATCC 6633 are resident to the study extracts.

Fungicidal properties studies of the medicinal and vegetable raw material extracts compositions were carried out on pure cultures of fungi *Cladosporium*, *Fusarium*, *Rhizopus*. The research results are presented in table 4.

Fungal cultures growth inhibition zones were noted in the studied samples of extract compositions: *Cladosporium* from 15 mm (oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and common St. John's wort extracts ratio is 1:1:1) to 28 mm (ratio 2:1:2); *Fusarium* from 18 mm (extracts' ratio is 1:1:1 and 1:1:2) to 30 mm (extracts' ratio is 2:1:2); *Rhizopus* from 16 mm (extracts' ratio is 1:1:1 and 1: 1: 2) to 30 mm (extracts' ratio is 2:1:2). It should be noted that the juniper berry extract concentration increasing has almost no effect on cultures' growth inhibiting. Oak bark and leaves and common St. John's wort extracts concentrations increasing in the composition allows the growth inhibition zone diameter increasing by 60–80%.

Table 4

Determination of compositions' fungicidal properties of oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and common St. John's wort extracts

Extracts composition	The diameter value of growth inhibition zone, mm		
	<i>Cladosporium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Rhizopus</i>
Oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and common St. John's wort extracts 1:1:1	15±0,38	18±0,41	18±0,40
Oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and common St. John's wort extracts 2:1:1	19±0,42	25±0,50	16±0,40
Oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and common St. John's wort extracts 1:2:1	19 ±0,41	20 ±0,50	18 ±0,41
Oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and common St. John's wort extracts 1:1:2	25 ±0,51	18 ±0,42	16 ±0,40
Oak bark and leaves, juniper berries and common St. John's wort extracts 2:1:2	28 ±0,53	30 ±0,44	20 ±0,41

The results of film-forming agent type effect on the mold fungi cultures' growth inhibiting are presented in table 5.

Table 5

Determination of film-forming agent type effect on the mold fungi cultures' growth inhibiting

The film composition	The diameter value of growth inhibition zone, mm		
	<i>Cladosporium</i>	<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>Rhizopus</i>
Extracts composition + chitosan	34,1±0,53	35,0±0,50	26,4±0,47
Extracts composition + methylcellulose	14,0±0,12	16,0±0,14	12,3±0,13
Extracts composition + sodium alginate	0,0±0,00	0,0±0,00	0,0±0,00

The obtained data analysis allows concluding that the film-forming composition on the chitosan base has the greatest fungistatic effect. Fungi growth inhibition zones are *Cladosporium* – 34,1 mm, *Fusarium* – 35,0 mm, *Rhizopus* – 26,4 mm. The methylcellulose adding reduces extracts' effect on microorganisms' growth inhibition. The film-forming composition with sodium alginate adding as a film-forming agent hasn't antimicrobial activity.

During fruits storage, respiratory gas exchange is generalizing indicator which reflects the metabolic processes intensity during storage. Undesirable overripeness and aging of fruits can be delayed by respiratory activity reducing, which helps to extend the storage period.

Fig. 1 Respiratory intensity dynamics of variety eggplants: a – Valentyna; b – Samurai; —◇— — K₁, —□— — K₂, —△— — chitosan

Fig. 2 Respiratory intensity dynamics of variety eggplants: a – Solaris; b – Clorinda; —◇— — K₁, —□— — K₂, —△— — chitosan

Figures 1, 2 present studies results of eggplant fruits respiratory intensity. Results analysis shows that eggplant fruits respiratory intensity depends on their variety. At the beginning of storage period the respiration rate of Solaris variety fruits (American agriculture) is 32,0 mg CO₂/kg·h; Clorinda variety (Egg agriculture) is 52,4 mg CO₂/kg·h; Valentyna and Samurai varieties (Japanese agriculture) are 62,4 and 69,0 mg CO₂/kg·h respectively. The film-forming composition on the base of low molecular weight chitosan use reduces respiratory intensity amplitude and allows storage period increasing by 2,0–2,3 times.

As research result the film-forming composition with antimicrobiological activity for eggplant fruits treatment on the base of medicinal and vegetable raw material extracts with use of low molecular weight water-soluble chitosan as a film-forming agent, was theoretically substantiated and experimentally proved.

Conclusion. The developed film-forming composition on the chitosan base allows it recommending for fresh eggplant fruits treatment with the aim of longer and better storage on the base of conducted researches and a number of positive results obtaining, namely, lack of toxicity, tested vegetables improved storage conditions compared to control sample and a wide range of antimicrobial activity.

References

1. Важенин Е. И. Влияние обработки электромагнитным полем крайне низкой частоты на сохранность и показатели качества томатов / Е. И. Важенин, Г. И. Касьянов, А. М. Гаджиева // Изв. вузов. Пищ. технология. – 2013. – №1. – С. 81–82.

Vazhenin, E., Kasyanov, G., Gadzhieva, A. (2013), «The effect of processing by an electromagnetic field of extremely low frequency on the safety and

quality indicators of tomatoes» [«Vliyaniye obrabotki elektromagnitnym polem krayne nizkoy chastoty na sokhrannost i pokazateli kachestva tomatov»], *Izv. universities. Food Technology*, No. 1, pp. 81-82.

2. Важенин Е. И. Влияние ЭМП КНЧ на микробиологические показатели качества плодовоощного сырья / Е. И. Важенин // Современная наука: актуальные проблемы и пути их решения : матер. 6-й Междунар. дистанц. науч. конф. – Липецк, 2013. – С. 3–5.

Vazhenin, E. (2013), «The effect of ELF EMF on microbiological indicators of the quality of fruit and vegetable raw materials» [«Vliyaniye EMP KNCH na mikrobiologicheskiye pokazateli kachestva plodoovoshchnogo syrya»], *Modern Science: Actual Problems and Solutions: Mater. 6th International Distance Scientific Conference*, Lipetsk, pp. 3-5.

3. Важенин Е. И. Перспективы использования в пищевой индустрии технологий с применением электромагнитных полей крайне низкой частоты / Е. И. Важенин, Г. И. Касьянов, А. В. Грачев // Политематический сетевой электронный научный журнал Кубанского государственного аграрного университета. – 2013. – № 85(01). – С. 140–153.

Vazhenin, E., Kasyanov, G., Grachev, A. (2013), «Prospects for the use in the food industry of technologies using electromagnetic fields of extremely low frequency» [«Perspektivy ispolzovaniya v pishchevoy industrii tekhnologiy s primeneniym elektromagnitnykh poley krayne nizkoy chastoty»], *Political Internet electronic scientific journal of the Kuban State Agrarian University*, No. 85(01), pp. 140-153.

4. Важенин Е. И. Совершенствование технологии хранения плодовоощного сырья / Е. И. Важенин, Г. И. Касьянов // Изв. вузов. Пищ. технология. – 2014. – № 1. – С. 13.

Vazhenin, E., Kasyanov, G., (2014), «Improving the technology of storage of fruits and vegetables» [«Sovershenstvovaniye tekhnologii khraneniya plodoovoshchnogo syrya»], *Izv. Universities. Food technology*, No. 1, p. 13.

5. Особенности использования электромагнитного поля крайне низкой частоты для хранения сельскохозяйственной продукции / Г. И. Касьянов, И. Е. Сязин, А. В. Грачев, Т. Н. Давыденко, Е. И. Важенин // Journal of Electromagnetic Analysis and Applications. – 2013. – № 55038. – С. 236–241.

Kasyanov, G., Syazin, I., Grachev, A., Davydenko, T., Vazhenin, E. (2013), “Features of using an electromagnetic field of extremely low frequency for storing agricultural products” [“Osobennosti ispolzovaniya elektromagnitnogo polya krayne nizkoy chastoty dlya khraneniya selskokhozyaystvennoy produktsii”], *Journal of Electromagnetic Analysis and Applications*, No. 55038, pp. 236-241.

6. Касьянов Г. И. Технология рыбоовощных продуктов / Г. И. Касьянов, О. В. Косенко, Е. И. Важенин. – Краснодар : Юг, 2014. – 128 с.

Kasyanov, G., Kosenko, O., Vazhenin, E. (2014), *Technology of fish and vegetable products [Tekhnologiya ryboovoshchnykh produktov]*, Publishing House. «South», Krasnodar, 128 p.

7. Яковлева Л. А. Перспективные направления предварительной обработки сельскохозяйственного сырья перед закладкой его на хранение / Л. А. Яковлева, Е. В. Веливанова // Инновационные пищевые технологии в области хранения и переработки сельскохозяйственного сырья / Научно-

исследовательский институт хранения и переработки сельскохозяйственной продукции. – Краснодар, 2011. – С. 57–61.

Yakovleva, L., Velivanova, E. (2011), «Prospective directions for the preliminary processing of agricultural raw materials before laying them for storage» [«Perspektivnyye napravleniya predvaritel'noy obrabotki selskokhozyaystvennogo syrya pered zakladkoj yego na khraneniye»], *Innovative food technologies in the field of storage and processing of agricultural raw materials*. Research Institute for Storage and Processing of Agricultural Products, Krasnodar, pp. 57-61.

8. Дас Б. К. Пожовкнення по краях і мікробна якість свіжорізаного салату айсберга з різними дезінфікуючими засобами та часом контакту / Б. К. Дас, Ю. В. Ким, Дж. В. Чой // Болгарський журнал сільськогосподарської науки. – 2011. – № 17 (1). – С. 55–62.

Das, B.K., Kim, J.G, Choi, J.W. (2011), «Edge browning and microbial quality of fresh-cut iceberg lettuce with different sanitizers and contact times» [«Pozhovkneniya po krayakh i mikrobnaya yakist svizhozrizanoho salatu z aysberha z riznymy dezinfikuuyuchymy zasobamy ta chasom kontaktu»], *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science*, No. 17 (1), pp. 55-62.

9. Важенин Е. И. Совершенствование процесса изготовления асептических биоразлагаемых упаковочных материалов / Е. И. Важенин // Наука в центральной России : матер. 4-й Междунар. конф. – Тамбов, 2013. – С. 39–42.

Vazhenin, E. (2013), «Improving the manufacturing process of aseptic biodegradable packaging materials» [«Sovershenstvovaniye protsessa izgotovleniya asepticheskikh birazlagayemykh upakovochnykh materialov»], *Science in Central Russia: Mater. 4th International Conference*, Tambov, pp. 39-42.

10. Влияние предобработки и упаковочного материала на физико-химические свойства и лежкость при хранении цветной капусты после солнечной сушки / Д. М. Кадам, Д. В. К. Самуил, П. Чандра, Х. С. Сикарвар // Food Science & Technology. – 2008. – № 43 (1). – С. 1–14.

Kadam, D.M., Samuel, D.V.K., Chandra, P., Sikarvar, H.S. (2008), «Impact of processing treatment and packaging material on some properties of stored dehydrated cauliflower» [«Vliyaniye predobrabotki i upakovochnogo materiala na fizikokhimicheskiye svoystva i lezhkost pri khraneni i tsvetnoy kapusty posle solnechnoy sushki»], *International Journal of Food Science & Tecnology*, No. 43(1), pp. 1-14.

11. Самми Ш. Влияние различных способов предобработки на качество плодов томата сорта Рио Гранде, хранившихся в полиэтиленовой пленке при комнатной температуре / Ш. Самми, Т. Масуд // Food Science & Technology. – 2008. – № 44 (5). – С. 918–926.

Sammi, S., Masud, T. (2008), «Effect of different packaging systems on the quality of tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* var. Rio Grande) fruits during storage» [«Vliyaniye razlichnykh sposobov predobrabotki na kachestvo plodov tomatata sorta Rio Grande, khranivshikhsya v polietilenovoy plenke pri komnatnoy temperature»], *International Journal of Food Science & Tecnology*, No. 44(5), pp. 918-926.

12. Экологически безопасные способы хранения овощей (В бактерицидной упаковке) / Касьянов Г. И., Маркелов А. В., Назарько М. Д.,

Франко Е. П. // Технология хранения и переработки сельскохозяйственного сырья. – Краснодар, 2010. – С. 139–142.

Kasyanov, G., Markelov, A., Nazarko, M., Franko, E. (2010), «Ecologically safe ways of storing vegetables (In bactericidal packaging)» [«Ekologicheski bezopasnyye sposoby khraneniya ovoshchey (V bakteritsidnoy upakovke)»], *Tekhnologiya khraneniya y pererabotky selskokhoziaistvennogo siria*, Krasnodar, pp. 139-142.

13. Важенин Е. И. Совершенствование процесса газожидкостной экстракции растительного сырья, обладающего асептическими свойствами хранению / Е. И. Важенин // Наука в центральной России : матер. 4-й Междунар. конф. – Тамбов, 2013. – С. 36–39.

Vazhenin, E. (2013), «Improving the process of gas-liquid extraction of plant materials with aseptic storage properties» [«Sovershenstvovaniye protsessa gazozhidkostnoy ekstraktsii rastitel'nogo syrya, obladayushchego asepticheskimi svoystvami khraneniya»], *Science in Central Russia: Mater. 4th International Conference*, Tambov, pp. 36-39.

14. Важенин Е. И. Разработка новейших видов CO₂-экстрактов из пряноароматического сырья / Е. И. Важенин, Г. И. Касьянов // Современные научные исследования и инновации в области применения суб- и сверхкритических технологий : сб. материалов междунар. науч.-техн. интернет-конф. – Краснодар, 2014. – С. 121–123.

Vazhenin, E., Kasyanov, G. (2014), «Development of the latest types of CO₂-extracts from aromatic raw materials» [«Razrabotka noveyshikh vidov SO₂-ekstraktov iz pryanoaromaticheskogo syrya»], *Modern scientific research and innovation in the application of sub- and supercritical technologies :Collection of materials of the international scientific and technical Internet conference*, Krasnodar, pp. 121-123.

15. Эффективность использования экстракта прополиса для обеззараживания при хранении минимально обработанной моркови / Камеяма О., Жуниор Ж. А., Тейшейра Ж. М. А., Андраде Н. Х., Минин В. П. Р., Соареш Л. С. // Церера. – 2008. – № 55 (3). – С. 218–223.

Kameyama, O., Abrao Junior, J., Teixeira, J.M. de A., De Andrade, N.J., Minim, V.P.R., Soares, L. dos S. (2008), «Extrato de propolis na sanitizacao e conservacao de cenoura minimamente processada» [«Effektivnost ispolzovaniya ekstrakta propolisa dlya obezrazhivaniya pri khraneni minimalno obrabotannoy morkovi»], *Ceres. Rev*, No. 55(3), pp. 218-223.

16. Соареш Н. де Ф. Ф. Влияние различных факторов на эффективность использования поглотителей кислорода при хранении продуктов питания / Соареш Н. де Ф. Ф., Круз Р. С., Андраде Н. Х. // Церера. – 2005. – № 300 (52). – С. 191–206.

Soares, N. de F.F., Cruz, R.S., Andrade, N.J. (2005), «Absorvedoes de Oxigenio na Conservacao de Alimentos: Uma Revjsao» [«Vliyaniye razlichnykh faktorov na effektivnost ispolzovaniya poglotiteley kisloroda pri khraneni produktov pitaniya»], *Rev. Ceres*, No. 300(52), pp. 191-206.

17. Лабинская А. С. Общая и санитарная микробиология с техникой микробиологических исследований / Лабинская А. С., Блинкова Л. П., Ещина А. С. – М. : Медицина, 2004. –588 с.

Labinskaya, A., Blinkova, L., Yeshchina, A. (2004), *General and sanitary microbiology with the technique of microbiological research [Obshchaya i sanitarnaya mikrobiologiya s tekhnikoj mikrobiologicheskikh issledovanij]*, Meditsina, Moscow, 588 p.

18. Лабинская А. С. Руководство по медицинской микробиологии. Общая санитарная микробиология. Кн. 1 / А. С. Лабинская, Е. Г. Волкова. – М. : Бином, 2008. – С. 345–567.

Labinskaya, A., Volkova, Ye., (2008), *Guide to medical microbiology. General Sanitary Microbiology [Rukovodstvo po meditsinskoj mikrobiologii. Obshchaya sanitarnaya mikrobiologiya, Kn. 1]*, Binom, Moscow, pp. 345-567.

19. Дудка И. А. Методы экспериментальной микологии : справочник / И. А. Дудка. – Киев : Наукова думка, 1982. – 552 с.

Dudka, Y. (1982), *Methods of experimental mycology: a handbook [Metody eksperimentalnoy mikologii: spravochnyk]*, Naukova dumka, Kyiv, 552 p.

20. Методы общей бактериологии : [пер. с англ. под ред. Ф. Герхардта и др. го]. – М. : Мир, 1984. – 536 с.

Gerkhardt, F. (ed.), et al. (1984), *Methods of general bacteriology [Metody obshchey bakteriologii]*, Mir, Moscow, 536 p.

21. Вивчення специфічної активності протимікробних лікарських засобів : методичні рекомендації / Волянський Ю. Л., Грищенко І. В., Широбоков В. П. та ін. – Київ, 2004. – 38 с.

Volianskiy, Yu., Hryshchenko, I., Shyrobokov, V., et al. (2004), *Study of the specific activity of antimicrobial drugs: guidelines [Vyvchennia spetsyfichnoi aktyvnosti protymikrobykh likarskykh zasobiv: metodychni rekomedatsii]*, Kyiv, 38 p.

Dubinina Antonina, Dr. of Tech. Sc., Prof., Department of Commodity Research and Expertise of Goods, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Klochkivska st., 333, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: tovaroved206@ukr.net.

Дубініна Антоніна Анатоліївна, д-р техн. наук, проф., кафедра товарознавства та експертизи товарів, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: вул. Клочківська, 333, м. Харків, Україна, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: tovaroved206@ukr.net.

Дубинина Антонина Анатольевна, д-р техн. наук, проф., кафедра товароведения и экспертизы товаров, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: ул. Клочковская, 333, г. Харьков, Украина, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: tovaroved206@ukr.net.

Letuta Tatiana, PhD in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Department of Commodity Research and Expertise of Goods, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Klochkivska st., 333, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: lettanya@ukr.net.

Летуга Тетяна Миколаївна, канд. техн. наук, проф., кафедра товарознавства та експертизи товарів, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: вул. Клочківська, 333, м. Харків, Україна, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: lettanya@ukr.net.

Летуга Татьяна Николаевна, канд. техн. наук, проф., кафедра товароведения и экспертизы товаров, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: ул. Клочковская, 333, г. Харьков, Украина, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: lettanya@ukr.net.

Frolova Tatiana, art. teacher, Department of Commodity Research and Expertise of Goods, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Klochkivska st., 333, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: 0502552621; e-mail: tetfrol70@ukr.net.

Фролова Тетяна Володимирівна, ст. викл., кафедра товарознавства та експертизи товарів, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: вул. Клочківська, 333, м. Харків, Україна, 61051. Тел.: 0502552621; e-mail: tetfrol70@ukr.net.

Фролова Татьяна Владимировна, ст. преп., кафедра товароведения и экспертизы товаров, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: ул. Клочковская, 333, г. Харьков, Украина, 61051. Тел.: 0502552621; e-mail: tetfrol70@ukr.net.

Skyrda Olena, PhD in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Department of Commodity Research and Expertise of Goods, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Klochkivska st., 333, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: sheva-forever@ukr.net.

Скирда Олена Євгенівна, канд. техн. наук, доц., кафедра товарознавства та експертизи товарів, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: вул. Клочківська, 333, м. Харків, Україна, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: sheva-forever@ukr.net.

Скирда Елена Евгеньевна, канд. техн. наук, доц., кафедра товароведения и экспертизы товаров, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: ул. Клочковская, 333, г. Харьков, Украина, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: sheva-forever@ukr.net.

Belyaeva Inna, Assoc. Prof., Department of Commodity Research and Expertise of Goods, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Klochkivska st., 333, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: ceascinna@gmail.com.

Беляева Инна Михайлівна, доц., кафедра товарознавства та експертизи товарів, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: вул. Клочківська, 333, м. Харків, Україна, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: ceascinna@gmail.com.

Беляева Инна Михайловна, доц., кафедра товароведения и экспертизы товаров, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: ул. Клочковская, 333, г. Харьков, Украина, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: ceascinna@gmail.com.

Popova Tatiana, PhD in Tech. Sc., Assoc. Prof., Department of Commodity Research and Expertise of Goods, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade. Address: Klochkivska st., 333, Kharkiv, Ukraine, 61051. Tel.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: popova.tatyana1@gmail.com.

Попова Тетяна Николаївна, канд. техн. наук, доц., кафедра товарознавства та експертизи товарів, Харківський державний університет харчування та торгівлі. Адреса: вул. Клочківська, 333, м. Харків, Україна, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: popova.tatyana1@gmail.com.

Попова Татьяна Николаевна, канд. техн. наук, доц., кафедра товароведения и экспертизы товаров, Харьковский государственный университет питания и торговли. Адрес: ул. Клочковская, 333, г. Харьков, Украина, 61051. Тел.: (057)349-45-48; e-mail: popova.tatyana1@gmail.com.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3937790

УДК 664.8.03:665.112:664.34

ЗМІНИ ВМІСТУ ВІТАМІНУ Е ПІД ЧАС ЗБЕРІГАННЯ МАЙОНЕЗІВ НА ОСНОВІ ОЛІЙ КУПАЖОВАНИХ

Ю.М. Хацкевич, Т.В. Щербакова, Г.А. Селютіна

Досліджено вміст вітаміну Е в майонезній продукції на основі олій купажованих залежно від співвідношення соняшникової та ріпакової олій. Проаналізовано зміни вмісту вітаміну Е під час зберігання майонезів. Показано, що всі зразки майонезів на основі олій купажованих після 90 діб зберігання містять значно більше вітаміну Е, ніж свіжовиготовлений зразок майонезу на основі рафінованої соняшникової олії. Зроблено висновок про доцільність використання олій купажованих у виробництві майонезної продукції.

Ключові слова: олії купажовані, ріпакова олія, поліненасичені жирні кислоти ряду ω -3 та ω -6, автоокиснення, α -токоферол, β -токоферол, δ -токоферол, γ -токоферол, гальмування автоокиснення.

ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ СОДЕРЖАНИЯ ВИТАМИНА Е ПРИ ХРАНЕНИИ МАЙОНЕЗОВ НА ОСНОВЕ МАСЕЛ КУПАЖИРОВАННЫХ

Ю.Н. Хацкевич, Т.В. Щербакова, Г.А. Селютіна

Исследовано содержание витамина Е в майонезной продукции на основе масел купажированных в зависимости от соотношения подсолнечного и рапсового масла. Проанализированы изменения содержания витамина Е при